

ADDITIVE BASES REPRESENTATIONS IN GROUPS

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Received: 1/2/07, Accepted: 4/27/07, Published: 8/1/08

Abstract

We show that the additive group of any finite field K of characteristic $\neq 2$ has a basis for which the number of representations of the elements of the field is bounded by a constant independent of K . We also establish a similar result for the additive group of any vector space V over a field of characteristic $\neq 2$. Moreover, if V is infinite, then the number of such representations never exceeds 2. We further prove that every modular group $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ has a basis for which the number of representations is bounded independently from n . Thus, in all these additive groups, the analogue of the Erdős-Turán conjecture for \mathbb{N} fails to hold.

– To Mel Nathanson on his 60th birthday

1. Introduction

The analogue of the Erdős-Turán conjecture [1, 2, 4], about the unboundedness of the number of representations by an additive basis of the natural numbers $\mathbb{N} = \{0, 1, \dots\}$, does not, in general, hold in abelian groups. This was first established by Puš [9], then remarkably extended by Nathanson [8]. To measure the extent to which it fails in a given semigroup S , we introduce the invariant $\tau(S)$, lying in $\overline{\mathbb{N}} = \mathbb{N} \cup \{\infty\}$. First, for a subset A of S and for $x \in S$, the number of representations of x by A is $r(A, x) = |\{(a, b) \in A \times A : a + b = x\}|$, and A is called a basis of S if $r(A, x) > 0$ for all $x \in S$. Let $s(A) = \sup\{r(A, x) : x \in S\}$. Then define $\tau(S) = \inf\{s(A) : A \in \mathbb{B}(S)\}$, where $\mathbb{B}(S)$ is the set of all bases of S . Clearly, $\tau(S) \geq 2$

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for a nontrivial S , and the minimum is attained in many cases. Thus, while the Erdős-Turán conjecture asserts that for the additive semigroup \mathbb{N} , we should have $\tau(\mathbb{N}) = \infty$, it follows from [7] that $\tau(\mathbb{Z}) = 2$, for the group of rational integers \mathbb{Z} .

Here, we give explicit bases for the additive group of the product of two fields, for which the number of representations is effectively bounded under proper conditions. In particular, $\tau(K \times K) = 2$ if K is an algebraically closed field of characteristic $\neq 2$ and $\tau(K \times K) \leq 18$ if K is a finite field of odd characteristic. We deduce that $\tau(V) = 2$ for the additive group of any infinite vector space V over a field of characteristic $\neq 2$. We also point to a simple relation between $\tau(\mathbb{N})$ and the sequence of $\tau(\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z})$, for the positive integers m and the corresponding modular groups $\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z}$, and using a method of Ruzsa [10], we prove that $\tau(\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z})$ is bounded by a constant independent of m (that is to say, absolutely bounded). We conclude that $\tau(\mathbb{F}_q)$ is also absolutely bounded, for all finite fields \mathbb{F}_q of odd characteristic. More generally, we deduce that $\tau(V)$ is absolutely bounded for the additive group of any vector space V over any field K of characteristic $\neq 2$.

2. Preliminary Results

Let S be an additive abelian semigroup, and A, B two subsets of S . For any $x \in S$, let $R(A, B; x) = \{(a, b) \in A \times B : a + b = x\}$ and $r(A, B; x) = |R(A, B; x)|$, where $|E|$ denotes the cardinality of the set E in $\overline{\mathbb{N}} = \mathbb{N} \cup \{\infty\}$. Let $s(A, B) = \sup\{r(A, B; x) : x \in S\}$. In particular, if $A = B$, we write $R(A, x), r(A, x)$ and $s(A)$ for $R(A, A; x), r(A, A; x)$ and $s(A, A)$, respectively. The *sumset* of A and B is defined as $A + B = \{a + b : (a, b) \in A \times B\}$. We say that B is a *basis* of A if $B \subset A \subset B + B$. The set of all bases of A is denoted by $\mathbb{B}(A)$. Now we define $\tau(A) = \inf\{s(B) : B \in \mathbb{B}(A)\}$, in $\overline{\mathbb{N}}$.

All intervals considered hereafter are in the set \mathbb{Z} of rational integers. The function $n \mapsto \tau([0, n])$, from \mathbb{N} into itself, is an increasing function which satisfies the property $\sup\{\tau([0, n]) : n \in \mathbb{N}\} = \tau(\mathbb{N})$ (see [2]).

The following simple results will be needed in the sequel.

Lemma 2.1. *Let S and T be additive abelian semigroups.*

- (1) *If $A = \bigcup_i A_i$ and $B = \bigcup_j B_j$ are unions of two families (A_i) and (B_j) of subsets of S , then $s(A, B) \leq \sum_{i,j} s(A_i, B_j)$.*
- (2) *If S is a group, A, B are subsets of S , and $u, v \in S$, then $s(u + A, v + B) = s(A, B)$.*
- (3) *If $S \times T$ is the product semigroup of S and T , then $\tau(S \times T) \leq \tau(S)\tau(T)$.*

Proof. (1) From the definitions, $R(A, B; x) = \bigcup_{i,j} R(A_i, B_j; x)$, so $r(A, B; x) \leq \sum_{i,j} r(A_i, B_j; x)$,

for all $x \in S$. The first inequality follows.

(2) For any $x \in S$, we have $R(u+A, v+B; x) = R(A, B; x-u-v)$, and thus $r(u+A, v+B; x) = r(A, B; x-u-v)$. Since $x \mapsto x-u-v$ is a permutation of the group S , the equality follows upon taking the supremum for $x \in S$, i.e. for $y = x-u-v$ ranging in S .

(3) For any $A \in \mathbb{B}(S)$ and $B \in \mathbb{B}(T)$, we have $A \times B \in \mathbb{B}(S \times T)$, and therefore $\tau(S \times T) \leq s(A \times B)$. Moreover, $r(A \times B, (s, t)) = r(A, s)r(B, t)$ for all $(s, t) \in S \times T$, and thus $s(A \times B) = s(A)s(B)$. The last inequality follows. \square

3. Products of Fields

Let K be a field. We denote by $K^* = K \setminus \{0\}$ the multiplicative group of K , by $\mathbb{S}(K^*) = \{x^2 : x \in K^*\}$ the subgroup of the square elements of K^* , and by $\iota(K) = (K^* : \mathbb{S}(K^*))$ the index of the subgroup $\mathbb{S}(K^*)$ in the group K^* . We also write $\mathbb{S}(K) = \mathbb{S}(K^*) \cup \{0\}$ for the set of all the squares in K . We consider the product group $K \times K$, of the additive group of K by itself, and the subsets $A(u) = \{(x, ux^2) : x \in K\}$ of $K \times K$, where $u \in K$.

Proposition 3.1. *Let K be a field of characteristic $\neq 2$. Let $t \in K \setminus \{0, -1\}$, and set $u = 1+t$, $v = 1+1/t$ and $w = u+v$. We then have*

- (1) $w \cdot \mathbb{S}(K) = t \cdot \mathbb{S}(K)$.
- (2) $A(u) + A(v) = \{(a, b) \in K \times K : (b - a^2) \in t \cdot \mathbb{S}(K)\}$.
- (3) $s(A(u)) = s(A(u), A(v)) = s(A(v)) = 2$.

Proof. (1) Clearly, $uv = u + v = w = (1+t)^2/t \neq 0$, so that $wt = (1+t)^2 \in \mathbb{S}(K^*)$. Therefore w and t are in the same coset of $\mathbb{S}(K^*)$ in K^* , and thus $w \cdot \mathbb{S}(K) = t \cdot \mathbb{S}(K)$.

(2-3) For any $u, v \in K$ such that $u + v \neq 0$, the set $A(u) + A(v)$ consists of the elements $(a, b) \in K \times K$ for which there exist $x, y \in K$ satisfying $x + y = a$ and $ux^2 + vy^2 = b$, i.e. such that the quadratic equation $ux^2 + v(a-x)^2 - b = 0$ has a solution x in K . This is equivalent to its discriminant $b(u+v) - a^2uv$ (to within a factor of 4) being a square in K . Moreover, the equation has at most two solutions in K , and it has exactly two in some cases such as for $a = 0$ and $b = u+v$, so that $s(A(u), A(v)) = 2$. In particular, for the choice of u and v made here, (a, b) lies in $A(u) + A(v)$ if and only if $w(b - a^2)$ is a square in K , i.e. $(b - a^2)$ lies in $w \cdot \mathbb{S}(K) = t \cdot \mathbb{S}(K)$. Moreover, since $2u$, $2v$ and $u + v$ are nonzero, $s(A(u)) = s(A(v)) = s(A(u), A(v)) = 2$. \square

Theorem 3.2. *Let K be a field of characteristic $\neq 2$ in which the index $\iota(K)$ is finite, equal to n . Let $\{t_i : 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ be a set of coset representatives of $\mathbb{S}(K^*)$ in K^* , with $t_1 = 1$, and assume that they satisfy the following conditions:*

$$(H) \quad (t_i + 1)(t_i + t_j + 2) \left(t_i + \frac{1}{t_j} + 2 \right) \left(\frac{1}{t_i} + \frac{1}{t_j} + 2 \right) \neq 0, \text{ for all } 1 \leq i, j \leq n.$$

Set $u_i = 1 + t_i$ and $v_i = 1 + \frac{1}{t_i}$, for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Then $B = \bigcup_{i=1}^n (A(u_i) \cup A(v_i))$ is a basis of the additive group $K \times K$ and $s(B) \leq 2(2n - 1)^2$.

Proof. By assumption, $K^* = \bigcup_{i=1}^n t_i \cdot \mathbb{S}(K^*)$ and therefore $K = \bigcup_{i=1}^n t_i \cdot \mathbb{S}(K)$. Hence, for any $(a, b) \in K \times K$, there exists $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ such that $(b - a^2) \in t_i \cdot \mathbb{S}(K)$, and therefore, in view of 3.1, $(a, b) \in A(u_i) + A(v_i)$. Thus $K \times K \subset \bigcup_{i=1}^n (A(u_i) + A(v_i)) \subset B + B$, i.e. B is a basis of $K \times K$. Moreover, the conditions (H) translate into: $u_i \neq 0$, $v_i \neq 0$, $u_i + u_j \neq 0$, $u_i + v_j \neq 0$ and $v_i + v_j \neq 0$, for all $1 \leq i, j \leq n$. So, by 3.1, $s(A(u_i), A(u_j)) = s(A(u_i), A(v_j)) = s(A(v_i), A(v_j)) = 2$, for all i, j . Note also that, since $t_1 = 1$, we have $u_1 = v_1 = 2$. Thus B is a union of at most $2n - 1$ distinct sets of the type $A(w_k)$, with $\{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{2n-1}\} = \{u_1, u_2, v_2, \dots, u_n, v_n\}$ and $s(A(w_k), A(w_l)) = 2$, for all $1 \leq k, l \leq 2n - 1$. Hence, by 2.1, $s(B) \leq \sum_{1 \leq k, l \leq 2n-1} s(A(w_k), A(w_l)) = 2(2n - 1)^2$. \square

Remark 3.3. For a field K , if the index $\iota(K)$ is finite, then it is a power of 2, since the quotient group $K^*/\mathbb{S}(K^*)$ is a 2-group (see [6]). In particular, if K is algebraically closed, this index is 1. If K is a finite field of characteristic $\neq 2$, this index is 2, since the map $x \mapsto x^2$ induces a group isomorphism from $K^*/\{\pm 1\}$ onto $\mathbb{S}(K^*)$. Note further that, given any power of 2, there exist fields K for which the index $\iota(K)$ is equal to that power of 2. The index can also be infinite as in the case of the field \mathbb{Q} of rational numbers.

Corollary 3.4. *Let K be a field of characteristic $\neq 2$ in which the index $\iota(K)$ is finite, equal to n . Then the additive group of $K \times K$ satisfies $\tau(K \times K) \leq 2(2n - 1)^2$.*

In particular, if K is finite, then $\tau(K \times K) \leq 18$.

Proof. If K is infinite, every coset $t \cdot \mathbb{S}(K^*)$ of $\mathbb{S}(K^*)$ in K^* is infinite, so that we may choose the coset representatives t_i in 3.2 to satisfy the conditions (H). Hence the existence of a basis B of $K \times K$ such that $s(B) \leq 2(2n - 1)^2$.

If K is finite, then $n = 2$, as noted in 3.3. So the conditions (H) boil down to the following ones: each of $t_2 + 1$, $t_2 + 3$, $3t_2 + 1$ is not zero, where t_2 lies in $K^* \setminus \mathbb{S}(K^*)$. These can be easily satisfied whenever $|K| \geq 7$. Indeed, if $K = \mathbb{F}_7 = \mathbb{Z}/7\mathbb{Z}$, then $K^* \setminus \mathbb{S}(K^*) = \{3, 5, 6\}$, and we may take $t_2 = 3$ or 5 . Otherwise, $|K| \geq 9$ and $K^* \setminus \mathbb{S}(K^*)$ contains 4 or more elements, among which one at least satisfies the three conditions imposed on t_2 . So, by 3.2, the additive group $K \times K$ has a basis B such that $s(B) \leq 18$. There remain the cases of $K = \mathbb{F}_p = \mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$, with $p = 3$ or 5 , where direct constructions yield bases B of $K \times K$ with $s(B)$ smaller than 18 (e.g. $B = A \times A$, where $A = \{0, 1, 2\}$). \square

Corollary 3.5. *If K is an algebraically closed field of characteristic $\neq 2$, then $\tau(K \times K) = 2$.*

This is just a special case of 3.4, in which the index $\iota(K) = 1$.

Remark 3.6. If the characteristic of K is 2, then the above results are not in general valid, since in that case, for any subset B of $K \times K$, we have $s(B) = r(B, (0, 0)) = |B|$.

The cases where K is either algebraically closed or is a finite field are contained in [3].

4. Modular Groups and Finite Fields

For a positive integer m , we consider the quotient ring $\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z}$ and the canonical homomorphism $\pi : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z}$, defined by $\pi(x) = \bar{x} = x + m\mathbb{Z}$ (in $\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z}$) for any $x \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Proposition 4.1. *Let m be a positive integer and A a finite non-empty subset of \mathbb{N} , with $a = \min(A)$ and $b = \max(A)$. Let $C = \pi(A)$.*

(1) *For any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have $r(C, \bar{n}) \leq \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} r(A, n + km)$.*

Moreover, $s(C) \leq ([2(b - a)/m] + 1) \cdot s(A)$, where $[x]$ is the largest integer $\leq x$, for a real number x .

(2) *If the restriction of π to A is injective (e.g. if $m > b - a$), then, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have $r(A, n) \leq r(C, \bar{n}) = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} r(A, n + km)$, and thus $s(A) \leq s(C)$.*

(3) *If $m > b$, then $r(C, \bar{n}) = r(A, n) + r(A, n + m)$ for $0 \leq n < m$, and thus $s(C) \leq 2 \cdot s(A)$.*

(4) *If $m > 2b$, then $r(C, \bar{n}) = r(A, n)$ for $0 \leq n < m$, and thus $s(C) = s(A)$.*

(5) *If $A \in \mathbb{B}([0, m - 1])$, then $C \in \mathbb{B}(\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z})$ and $s(A) \leq s(C) \leq 2s(A)$.*

Proof. (1) We have $R(C, \bar{n}) = \{(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) \in C \times C : \bar{x} + \bar{y} = \bar{n}\} = \bigcup_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \{(\bar{x}, \bar{y}) \in C \times C : x + y = n + km\} = \pi \times \pi (\bigcup_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} R(A, n + km))$, so that $r(C, \bar{n}) \leq \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} r(A, n + km)$. Moreover, the latter summation can be restricted to the integers k in the interval $[(2a - n)/m, (2b - n)/m]$, since $r(A, n + km) = 0$ for $n + km$ outside $[2a, 2b]$ which contains $A + A$. But the number of integers k in the former interval is $\leq [2(b - a)/m] + 1$. Hence $\sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} r(A, n + km) \leq ([2(b - a)/m] + 1) \cdot s(A)$, and the result follows.

(2) In this case, the map π induces a bijection from A onto C , so that, in view of the proof of (1), $R(C, \bar{n})$ is in bijection, via $\pi \times \pi$, with the disjoint union of sets $\bigcup_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} R(A, n + km)$. This yields the result.

(3) and (4) follow from (2), since $r(A, x) = 0$ for $x > 2b$ or $x < 0$.

(5) follows from (2) and (3). \square

Corollary 4.2. *For any positive integer m , we have $\tau(\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z}) \leq 2\tau([0, m-1])$.*

Indeed, by 4.1, (5), for any $A \in \mathbb{B}([0, m-1])$, we have $\pi(A) \in \mathbb{B}(\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z})$ and $s(\pi(A)) \leq 2s(A)$, which yields the result.

Corollary 4.3. *We have $\sup\{\tau(\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z}) : m \geq 1\} \leq 2\tau(\mathbb{N})$.*

This follows from 4.2 and the property $\tau(\mathbb{N}) = \sup\{\tau([0, n]) : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$, established in ([2], 3.4).

Remark 4.4. In view of 4.3, if the sequence $(\tau(\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z}))_{m \geq 1}$ were unbounded, then $\tau(\mathbb{N})$ would be infinite, i.e. the Erdős-Turán conjecture in \mathbb{N} would hold. However, as will be shown below, this is not the case.

Definition 4.5. For a subset E of \mathbb{Z} , the *size* of E is the number of its elements, the *interior size* of E is the largest size of intervals contained in E , and the *exterior size* of E is the smallest size of intervals containing E . The three “sizes” coincide when E is an interval of \mathbb{Z} .

Lemma 4.6. *Let n be a positive integer, C a subset of \mathbb{Z} and $B = \pi(C)$.*

- (1) *If the interior size of $C + C$ is $\geq n$, then B is a basis of $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$.*
- (2) *If the exterior size of $C + C$ is $\leq qn$, for some positive integer q , then $s(B) \leq q \cdot s(C)$.*

Proof. (1) In the first case, $C + C \supset I$ where I is an interval of size n . Hence $B + B = \pi(C + C) \supset \pi(I) = \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$, so that B is a basis of $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$.

(2) In the second case, $C + C \subset J$ where J is an interval of size qn . Hence, for any $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$, we have $R(B, \bar{x}) = \pi \times \pi(\bigcup_{y \in Y} R(C, y))$, where $Y = \pi^{-1}(\bar{x}) \cap (C + C) \subset \pi^{-1}(\bar{x}) \cap J$, and $|Y| \leq |\pi^{-1}(\bar{x}) \cap J| = |\{x + kn \in J : k \in \mathbb{Z}\}| \leq q$ since $|J| = qn$. Therefore $r(B, \bar{x}) \leq |Y| \cdot s(C) \leq q \cdot s(C)$, for all $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$, and the result follows. \square

The following result is an adaptation of section 3 of Ruzsa’s paper [10].

Proposition 4.7. *For any odd prime number p , there exists a subset C of \mathbb{Z} of exterior size $\leq 4p^2$ such that the interior size of $C + C$ is $\geq 2p^2$ and $s(C) \leq 288$.*

Proof. We identify the elements of $\mathbb{F}_p = \mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$ with the integers $0, 1, \dots, p-1$, consider the additive group $G = \mathbb{F}_p \times \mathbb{F}_p$ and define the map $f : G \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ by $f(a, b) = a + 2pb$. Then f is an injective map and $f(G) \subset [0, 2p^2 - p]$.

For any elements $(s, t), (v, w), (s', t'), (v', w')$ in G , if $f(s, t) + f(v, w) = f(s', t') + f(v', w')$, then $(s, t) + (v, w) = (s', t') + (v', w')$. Indeed, the first equality implies that $|2p(t+w-t'-w')| = |s' + v' - s - v| < 2p$, so that $t + w - t' - w' = s' + v' - s - v = 0$, which yields the second equality. It follows that $s(f(X)) \leq s(X)$, for any subset X of G .

By 3.4, there exists a basis B of G such that $s(B) \leq 18$. Let $A = f(B)$. Then $s(A) \leq s(B) \leq 18$. Given $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$ be such that $n = a + 2pb$ and $0 \leq a < 2p$ (Euclidean division), and let (\bar{a}, \bar{b}) be the canonical image of (a, b) in G , i.e. $\bar{a} \equiv a \pmod{p}$ and $\bar{b} \equiv b \pmod{p}$, where $0 \leq \bar{a}, \bar{b} \leq p - 1$. Since B is a basis of G , there exist two elements (x, y) and (x', y') in B such that $(x, y) + (x', y') = (\bar{a}, \bar{b})$, so that $x + x' \equiv a \pmod{p}$, $y + y' \equiv b \pmod{p}$ and $0 \leq x + x', y + y' \leq 2(p - 1)$. Therefore $x + x' - a = ip$ and $y + y' - b = jp$, with integers i, j such that $-2 < i \leq 1$ and $-b/p \leq j \leq 1$. In particular, if n lies in the interval $[0, 2p^2[$, then $b < p$ and $-1 < j \leq 1$. Moreover, setting $u = f(x, y)$ and $u' = f(x', y')$, we have $u, u' \in A$ and $u + u' - n = x + x' - a + 2p(y + y' - b) = ip + 2jp^2$, with $-1 \leq i \leq 1$ and $0 \leq j \leq 1$, so that $n - (u + u')$ lies in $E = \{-2p^2 - p, -2p^2, -2p^2 + p, -p, 0, p\}$. Thus every integer $n \in [0, 2p^2[$ lies in the set $A + A + E$.

Let $D = \{-2p^2, -p, 0, p\}$ and $C = A + D$. Since $D + D \supset E$, then $C + C$ contains $A + A + E$, which contains $[0, 2p^2[$, so that the interior size of $C + C$ is $\geq 2p^2$. Since $A \subset f(G) \subset [0, 2p^2 - p[$, then C is contained in $[-2p^2, 2p^2[$, so that the exterior size of C is $\leq 4p^2$. Moreover, C being the union of 4 translates of A , by 2.1, we have $s(C) \leq 4^2 s(A) \leq 16 \cdot 18$. \square

Theorem 4.8. *There exists an absolute constant $c > 1$ such that $\tau(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}) \leq c$, for all positive integers n .*

Proof. Assume first that $n \geq 8$. Let $m = \lceil \sqrt{n/2} \rceil$. By Bertrand's postulate [5], there exists an odd prime number p such that $m < p \leq 2m$. Then $n \leq 2p^2$ and $p^2 \leq 2n$. By 4.7, there exists a subset C of \mathbb{Z} of exterior size $\leq 4p^2 \leq 8n$ such that the interior size of $C + C$ is $\geq 2p^2 \geq n$ and $s(C) \leq 288$. So, by 4.6, the canonical image $B = \pi(C)$ of C is a basis of $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$, and $s(B) \leq 8 \cdot s(C) \leq 8 \cdot 288 = c$. Hence $\tau(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}) \leq c$ for $n \geq 8$, and the inequality holds trivially for $n < 8$. \square

Corollary 4.9. *The additive group of any finite field F of characteristic $\neq 2$ satisfies $\tau(F) \leq 18c$. Thus $\tau(F)$ is absolutely bounded over the class of all such finite fields F .*

Proof. Let $F = \mathbb{F}_q$ be a finite field of characteristic $p \neq 2$, with $q = p^n$ elements, where n is the dimension of \mathbb{F}_q over \mathbb{F}_p .

If n is even, $n = 2m$ with an integer $m > 0$, then \mathbb{F}_q is isomorphic to $\mathbb{F}_{p^m} \times \mathbb{F}_{p^m}$ as an \mathbb{F}_p -vector space and as an additive group. Hence $\tau(\mathbb{F}_q) = \tau(\mathbb{F}_{p^m} \times \mathbb{F}_{p^m}) \leq 18$, by 3.4.

If n is odd, $n = 2m + 1$ with an integer $m \geq 0$, then \mathbb{F}_q is isomorphic to $\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}} \times \mathbb{F}_p$. Hence $\tau(\mathbb{F}_q) = \tau(\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}} \times \mathbb{F}_p) \leq \tau(\mathbb{F}_{p^{2m}})\tau(\mathbb{F}_p) \leq 18\tau(\mathbb{F}_p) \leq 18c$, in view of 2.1, the above result for n even, and 4.8. \square

Remark 4.10. The value of the absolute constant $c = 8 \cdot 288 = 2304$, which appears in 4.8 and 4.9, can presumably be lowered. Some examples of values for $\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}$ are:

$$\tau(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}) = \begin{cases} 2, & \text{if } n = 2, 3 \\ 3, & \text{if } n = 4, 5, 7 \\ 4, & \text{if } n = 6 \text{ or } 8 \leq n \leq 15 \\ 5, & \text{if } 16 \leq n \leq 19 \text{ or } n = 23 \\ 6, & \text{if } n = 20, 21, 22, 24, 25 \end{cases}$$

Furthermore, in view of the inequality in 4.2 and the computations made in [2], we have

$$\tau(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}) \leq 8 \text{ for } n \leq 46,$$

$$\tau(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}) \leq 10 \text{ for } n \leq 60,$$

$$\tau(\mathbb{Z}/n\mathbb{Z}) \leq 12 \text{ for } n \leq 224.$$

5. Vector Spaces

Theorem 5.1. *If V is an infinite vector space over a field K of characteristic $\neq 2$, then the additive group of V satisfies $\tau(V) = 2$.*

Proof. Let F be the prime subfield of K .

If V is uncountable, then it is infinite-dimensional over F . Hence V is isomorphic to $V \times V$ as a vector space over F . Now, there is an algebraically closed field L which is an extension of the field F and such that V is isomorphic to L as a vector space over F . So V and $L \times L$ are isomorphic as vector spaces over F and, therefore, also as abelian groups. Thus $\tau(V) = \tau(L \times L) = 2$, in view of 3.5. Indeed, the field L can be obtained as follows. By adjoining to F enough transcendental elements over F , one gets a field extension E , purely transcendental over F , isomorphic to V as a vector space over F . Now the algebraic closure L of E has the same cardinality as E (see [6]), hence the equality between degrees $[L : F] = [E : F]$, since E is uncountable and F is countable. So L is isomorphic to E , and thus to V , as a vector space over F .

If V is denumerable, then the additive group of V is a countably infinite abelian group such that the set $\{2v : v \in V\}$ is infinite (since the characteristic of K is not 2), so that by [8], V has a basis B such that $s(B) = 2$, and therefore $\tau(V) = 2$. \square

Corollary 5.2. *The additive group of any vector space V over a field K of characteristic $\neq 2$ satisfies $\tau(V) \leq 18c$, where c is the absolute constant in 4.8.*

Thus $\tau(V)$ is absolutely bounded over the class of all such vector spaces V .

Proof. If V is infinite, then $\tau(V) = 2$ by 5.1. On the other hand, the additive group of a finite vector space V over a field K is isomorphic to the additive group of a finite field with the same characteristic, and the result follows from 4.9. \square

Corollary 5.3. *The invariant $\tau(K)$ is absolutely bounded over the class of all fields K of characteristic $\neq 2$. In particular, if K is infinite, then $\tau(K) = 2$.*

References

1. P. Erdős and P. Turán, *On a problem of Sidon in additive number theory, and on some related problems*, J. London Math. Soc. **16** (1941), 212-215; MR 3,270e.
2. G. Grekos, L. Haddad, C. Helou, J. Pihko, *On the Erdős-Turán conjecture*, J. Number Theory **102** (2003), 339-352.
3. L. Haddad and C. Helou, *Bases in some additive groups and the Erdős-Turán conjecture*, J. Combinatorial Theory, series A **108** (2004), 147-153.
4. H. Halberstam and K. F. Roth, *Sequences*, Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1966; MR 35 1565.
5. G. H. Hardy and E. M. Wright, *An introduction to the theory of numbers*, 5th edition, Oxford University Press, 1979; MR 81i:10002.
6. S. Lang, *Algebra*, Revised third edition, Springer, New York, 2002; MR 2003e:00003.
7. M. B. Nathanson, *Unique representation bases for the integers*, Acta Arith. **108** (2003), 1-8.
8. M. B. Nathanson, *Representation functions of additive bases for abelian semigroups*, Int. J. Math. Math. Sci. **2004:30** (2004), 1589-1597.
9. V. Puš, *On multiplicative bases in abelian groups*, Czech. Math. J. **41** (1991), 282-287.
10. I. Z. Ruzsa, *A just basis*, Monatsh. Math. **109** (1990), 145-151; MR 91e:11016.